

ENHANCING VOCAL IMPROVISATION THROUGH INTERACTIVE MEDIA IN DRAMA PERFORMANCE – INSIGHTS FROM KINESTHESIS TOOLS 2.0 SYNERGIZED WITH SOMAX2

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores how interactive media—specifically Kinesthesia 2.0, a system for real-time vocal modulation via gesture and facial expression—enhances vocal improvisation in drama performance when integrated with the AI improvisation system Somax2. Grounded in the embodied practices of Greek tragedy (schemata) and Kathakali theater (mudras and Navarasam), Kinesthesia 2.0 transforms performers into co-creators: closing the right eye triggers reverb, the left eye activates reverse delay, and opening the mouth scales multi-tap delay, while hand gestures map to pitch and harmonic shifts. Integrated with Somax2’s generative clarinet responses, trained on Epirotic lament motifs, the system fosters human-AI co-improvisation, as demonstrated in Antigone’s Lament. We describe the technical architecture (MediaPipe, Max/MSP), artistic applications, and broader implications for interactive storytelling, demonstrating how such tools redefine the performer’s role in contemporary drama.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of kinesthetic learning and its application in the arts, particularly in theater and performance, has deep historical roots. Gesture, vocal expression, and facial expression are crucial for expressive performance in drama, encompassing aspects of nonverbal behavior such as vocalics, kinesics, proxemics, haptics, and chronemics [1]. The origins of theater can be traced back to early human storytelling, where rituals and symbolic gestures were employed to explore identity and communal experiences. These early forms of expression laid the groundwork for the formalization of theater in Ancient Greece, where elements like tragedy and comedy emerged during religious festivals. [2]

Choral poets, whether composing virginals, dithyrambs, or euphemisms, used the choral form to guide the audience’s imagination, transforming visible space into a spectral one. In this context, the ability of the Greek chorus to “imitate” voices and rhythmic movement transcended

local and geographical boundaries, offering a holistic representation of diverse idioms. This universality allowed audiences to identify with the dance, enhancing their emotional and intellectual engagement with the performance [3]. Greek schemata, codified gestures performed on stage, further exemplify the intricate relationship between physicality and cognition in performance. These gestures operated on multiple levels, simultaneously conveying emotion, advancing the narrative, and emphasizing the act of performance itself. By grounding performance in physical movement, schemata embodied the cognitive and emotional dimensions of storytelling, creating a layered interaction between performers and audiences [4].

This integration of embodied cognition into technological frameworks not only preserves the symbolic richness of schemata but also expands their application in contemporary performance. For example, a raised hand might modulate pitch, while a facial expression could adjust reverb, creating a dynamic interplay between movement and sound that engages the audience on multiple sensory levels.

The interplay between physicality and cognition is reflected in the principles of embodied cognition, which posits that thought and creativity are deeply intertwined with physical experiences. In performance, gestures function as cognitive tools, translating abstract intentions into tangible actions that bridge the performer’s intent with the audience’s interpretation [4]. Musical gestures, whether physical or metaphorical, amplify the relationship between body and sound, transforming performances into multisensory experiences. These principles resonate with the traditions of Greek tragedy, where physical movement, such as schemata, played a central role in storytelling and emotional expression.

Building on these traditions, the development of interactive “Drama Prosodic Tools” marked a significant milestone in redefining performance practices. These tools, inspired by ancient Greek prosody, incorporated gesture and voice dynamics to enrich the vocal and gestural performance of Attic tragic poetry. Notable systems, such as the Aristoxenus Tool and the Ancient Dialogues Drama Tool, utilized advanced pitch and dynamic detection alongside gesture tracking to extend vocal techniques and integrate interactivity into live performance [5], [6]. These early innovations laid the groundwork for more advanced sys-

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tems, demonstrating how technology could be used to reconstruct prosodic elements of ancient texts while offering performers new avenues for creative expression.

By introducing Kinesthesia tools into drama performance, this work demonstrates how technology has redefined the relationship between physicality and storytelling. Kinesthesia incorporates codified gestures into its design, echoing the symbolic richness of *schemata* while expanding their application in contemporary performance. For instance, a raised hand might modulate pitch, while a facial expression could adjust reverb, creating a dynamic interplay between movement and sound that engages the audience on multiple sensory levels. These tools enable performers to modulate sound dynamically through physical movements and facial expressions, drawing from theories of embodied cognition to emphasize the body's integral role in narrative expression.

Kinesthesia 2.0, an advanced iteration of the system, introduces refined gesture tracking and multisensory integration, bridging the gap between traditional practices and interactive media. Furthermore, its integration with AI systems like Somax2 fosters co-creative environments that expand artistic possibilities. These advancements emphasize the tragical dimension of dramatic texts through nonverbal modalities, including haptics, chronemics, and vocalics, connecting traditional practices such as Greek *schemata* [4] with modern technologies. By doing so, Kinesthesia reaffirms the body's central role in dramatic storytelling, blending ancient traditions with modern innovation to create immersive, multisensory experiences that resonate with audiences on a profound level.

2. BRIDGING INTERCULTURAL DRAMA PERFORMANCE THROUGH INTERACTIVE MEDIA

Kinesthesia 2.0 situates itself at the intersection of tradition and innovation. The performer's role as an improviser recalls the practices of classical and jazz musicians, where spontaneity and creativity are paramount.

At the same time, the use of advanced technologies, such as MediaPipe and OpenCV, integrates the contemporary possibilities of electroacoustic music into live performance.

By synthesizing these elements, Kinesthesia 2.0 transforms improvisation into an act of real-time composition, where the performer not only interprets but invents. This dual role elevates the performer from a medium of expression to a creator of immersive, multisensory experiences.

2.1 Gesture Control and Narrative Expression

The gesture control in Kinesthesia 2.0 draws extensively from the codified languages of movement found in both ancient Greek tragedy and Indian Kathakali. In Greek theater, *schemata*—a structured system of symbolic poses and movements—played a critical role in amplifying dramatic narratives. These gestures alternated between fluid dynamic actions (*phorai*) and striking, sculptural poses, creating a performative aesthetic that balanced storytelling

with visual impact. Beyond their narrative function, *schemata* possessed a metatheatrical quality, calling attention to the artifice of performance and engaging audiences in a layered, intellectual experience. [4] Similarly, Kathakali's *mudras* provide a meticulously developed gestural language rooted in the *Natyashastra*. With 24 foundational *Hasta Mudras*, Kathakali performers convey detailed narratives while evoking emotional states (*Bhavas*) that resonate as corresponding emotional experiences (*Rasas*) in the audience. [7], [8] This intricate system integrates hand gestures, body postures, eye movements, and rhythmic dynamics to form a multisensory storytelling medium. Kinesthesia 2.0 synthesizes these traditions by incorporating *schemata* to design codified symbolic movements and *mudras* as a gestural vocabulary, enabling performers to create immersive and culturally enriched interactions. While Kinesthesia 2.0 currently integrates elements from Greek tragedy and Indian Kathakali, its design could potentially be expanded to engage with codified traditions such as Japanese Noh theatre. Given Noh's highly preserved and rigidly defined gestural and musical vocabulary, such an application would necessitate careful adaptation to maintain cultural authenticity while exploring new interactive possibilities.

2.2 Facial Expression and Emotional Resonance

The facial expression control in Kinesthesia 2.0 is deeply inspired by the ancient Greek tragic mask, see Fig. 1, and the Navarasam of Kathakali, two traditions that exem-

Figure 1. Greek tragic masks.

plify the power of facial expression in performance. The Greek tragic mask, with its exaggerated yet minimalistic features, was designed to evoke a spectrum of emotions, such as sorrow, anger, or joy. [9] These static masks, as revealed by historical and neuroscientific analyses, relied on subtle tilts, lighting, and the movements of actors to create an illusion of animation. This interplay activated the audience's mirror neurons, enhancing empathetic en-

agement and transforming the mask into a dynamic storytelling tool. [10]

In parallel, the Navarasam, see Fig. 2,

Figure 2. 9 Navarasam.

offers a codified system of nine emotional states: love, anger, compassion, joy, fear, disgust, heroism, wonder and peace; expressed through precise facial muscle control and eye movements. [7], [8]The rigorous training of Kathakali performers to articulate these emotions with clarity inspired the integration of Navarasam into Kinesthesia 2.0. By combining the Greek emphasis on symbolic amplification with Kathakali’s precise emotional articulation, Kinesthesia 2.0 employs facial expression recognition not only as a technical tool but also as a means of conveying profound emotional depth, bridging the worlds of ancient theatrical traditions and modern interactive performance.

3. KINESTHESIS TOOLS: ARCHITECTURE, INTERFACE DESIGN AND ARTISTIC EXPRESSION

3.1 Kinesthesia

The Kinesthesia augmented voice tool is a gesture control system designed to enhance vocal improvisation. It consists of (i) a wireless microphone for capturing the voice, (ii) an external sound card, (iii) a computer, and (iv) the Kinect Sensor v1. [11] The system collects gestural data in real-time and interfaces with an audio processing patch to transform the human voice into an augmented musical instrument. A demonstration video is available online: Kinesthesia Demonstration¹.

¹ <https://youtu.be/kD98x8NOzn4?feature=shared>

It utilizes Processing 3.0, a graphical library and development environment in Java, along with the Open Kinect for Processing library, to process raw depth data and three-dimensional vectors (PVector). The OSC5 library transmits OSC (Open Sound Control) messages via UDP to a Max/MSP patch, which processes x, y, and z coordinates in real time, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Kinesthesia Max/MSP Patch.

These parameters control volume (x), pitch (y, spanning four octaves), and effect intensity (z, such as reverse delay), enabling precise hand gesture manipulation of sound on an xyz axis, see Fig. 4. The microphone-captured audio serves as the source material, while arm gestures act as computational inputs. These inputs are deciphered and re-configured to trigger sounds and automate effects, creating a seamless human and computer interaction. [10]

Figure 4. Kinesthesia Max/MSP and Sensor’s Integration.

3.2 Kinesthesia 2.0

Kinesthesia 2.0 is an advanced iteration of the original tool, designed for real-time vocal augmentation during performances. This system enables singers and actors to dynamically modify their voices, seamlessly integrating technology with artistic expression. It combines a facial expression and hand gesture detection system, developed in Python using MediaPipe, with a suite of vocal effects created in MAX/MSP, including a four-voice vocoder, pitch-shifter, reverb, multi-tap delay, and reverse delay, see Fig. 5.

By tracking movements and mapping them to control parameters for vocal effects, Kinesthesia 2.0 allows perform-

Figure 5. Kinesthesia 2.0 Max/MSP Patch.

ers to achieve real-time four-voice harmonization and precise modulation of sound. Helps integrate sensory information and strengthens muscle memory. [10] Inspired by Kathakali, the system incorporates gestures and facial expressions to produce complex vocal timbres and rhythms, enhancing the immersive experience of theater.

The system uses MediaPipe’s Holistic model (468 facial landmarks, 21 hand keypoints) with OpenCV at 640×480 resolution, achieving a measured end-to-end latency of 11.05ms (± 2.1 ms) via software timestamps (Python’s `time.time()` and Max/MSP’s `[adstatus]`). Normalized coordinates (0-127) and gesture states are streamed via zero-copy OSC/UDP (`localhost:32000`) to Max/MSP, where they map to audio parameters with 1.45ms buffer sizes: pitch (y-axis \rightarrow `mtof`, ± 4 octaves), reverb (z-axis \rightarrow `ffverb` for efficient decay), and delay (x-axis \rightarrow pre-allocated `tapin` with 4-tap feedback). Gestures (Fist, One, etc.) enable instant preset switching (< 2 ms response time), while continuous motion data drives spectral effects via line for artifact-free modulation. The system demonstrates consistent sub-20ms latency, with component-wise performance detailed in Fig. 6

Component	Mean Latency (ms) (ms)	Measurement Method
Camera Capture	2.1	Python <code>time.time()</code>
MediaPipe Processing	7.3	Python <code>time.time()</code>
OSC Transmission	0.2	Python <code>time.time()</code>
Max/MSP Audio Pipeline	1.45	Max <code>[adstatus]</code>
Total System	11.05	Aggregate (100 trials)

Figure 6. Component-wise latency measurements. *Measured on a MacBook Pro (M2, 2023) over 100 trials.*

MediaPipe is used for real-time hand and face tracking, see Fig. 7 while OpenCV processes webcam input to capture facial-expressions and physical gestures, enriching the performance experience. [12]

Figure 7. Facial Expression and Gesture Motion Capture for Real-Time Control.

The tool features a user-friendly Max/MSP interface, offering control over pitch-shifting options (transposer, gizmo, bypass) and a MIDI instrument mode (harmonic, in-between, percussive). Users can customize reverse delay, multi-tap delay, and parametric reverb, with real-time adjustments achieved through OSC messages transmitted via UDP. [14] These messages dynamically control pitch, delay effects, and reverb parameters such as size, decay time, damping, and diffusion, enabling performers to create expressive and dynamic soundscapes. A demonstration video is available online: Kinesthesia 2.0 Demo².

3.2.1 Key Features

The Kinesthesia 2.0 system offers several key features that enhance performative interactivity. a) Gesture modulation enables performers to control auditory parameters such as pitch, harmonic layering, and dynamics using hand movements, allowing for precise sound expression. b) Facial expression mapping links subtle expressions, such as raised eyebrows or smiles, to auditory modifications in timbre and spatial effects, adding an emotional and aesthetic layer to performances. c) Real-time feedback ensures immediate auditory responses, creating a dynamic and immersive interaction between the performer and the system. d) The system expands the gesture vocabulary by incorporating symbolic movements inspired by Kathakali theater and Greek schemata, enriching narrative expression and deepening audience engagement.

3.2.2 Related Work

Kinesthesia 2.0 builds upon a lineage of artistic and technological efforts to enhance vocal performance and bodily expression through interactive systems. Several pioneering artists and researchers have explored the intersection of gesture, voice, and digital technology, often seeking to blur the boundaries between body, instrument, and narrative. Pamela Z, for instance, has developed a rich body of installation works using the Body Synth MIDI controller to trigger sampled sounds with her own bodily gestures, creating immersive audio-visual environments [13]. Similarly, Hildegard Westerkamp’s *MotherVoiceTalk* uses the compositional affordances of the studio to negotiate the

² <https://youtu.be/8id1JKnTVoA>

boundaries between the intimate and the public, transforming autobiographical narratives into multisensory sonic experiences [14]. These works exemplify how voice and body can be reimagined through intermedial performance practices. Simon Emmerson's *Sentences* (1990), a seminal work for soprano and live electronics, was among the first to extend the timbral world of the human voice through real-time spatial processing [15]. His reflections on pre-linguistic vocalizations—such as grunts, groans, sighs, and screams—resonate with Kinesthesis 2.0's focus on amplifying embodied affect through dynamic voice manipulation [16]. From a gestural control perspective, technologies such as Imogen Heap's Mi.Mu gloves, [17] the eMic, [18] and Wekinator [19] have demonstrated how bodily motion can serve as input for live sound manipulation. The Mi.Mu gloves use inertial and flex sensors to enable expressive musical control through hand gestures, [17] while Wekinator allows real-time machine learning mappings between gestural inputs and sound synthesis parameters. While these systems offer powerful paradigms for gesture-based control and vocal augmentation, Kinesthesis 2.0 distinguishes itself through a wireless, markerless design that eliminates the need for physical sensors or wearables. Unlike glove-based systems (e.g., Mi.Mu's inertial sensors) or tools reliant on pre-trained models (e.g., Wekinator), it leverages real-time facial and hand tracking via MediaPipe, enabling unencumbered, full-body expressivity. This approach minimizes performative friction while embedding codified traditions (e.g., Kathakali mudras, Greek schemata) into its gesture vocabulary—bridging cultural heritage with computational flexibility. By integrating facial expression mapping (absent in Mi.Mu) and achieving sub-20ms audio modulation (see Sec.3.2), the system uniquely supports narrative-driven improvisation—a departure from prior tools focused solely on musical or compositional control.

3.3 Application of Kinesthesis tools in theater performance

3.3.1 *Kolokotronis Memoirs*

Kinesthesis augmented vocal tool was applied in the interactive theatrical documentary *Kolokotronis Memoirs* in 2021 for 21 performances from 27th of July till the 16th of August and took place in the History Museum of National and Kapodistrian University of Athens. In this historical drama, Kinesthesis tool enabled performers to create layered soundscapes through gesture. Gestures controlled harmonic shifts and spatial effects. The integration of movement and sound deepened the emotional resonance of the narrative, engaging audiences in a multisensory experience. [11]

3.3.2 *Rayman Scream*

Kinesthesis 2.0 was used for the first time in the theatre performance "Reyman Scream" (March 2024, Theatre "Sfendoni", Athens), as a vocal augmentation system, offering to the performer the ability to improvise and composing music in real-time. On the rehearsals, the theatrical

ensemble has used Kinesthesis 2.0 real-time voice automation and expressive features to dynamically modulate the soprano singer's and the main actor's vocal output, creating a harmonious blend and simulating a digital choir, synchronizing vocal elements with dramatic expressions. This demonstration highlighted the visceral connection between physicality and sound, emphasizing the performer's body as an expressive instrument of communication. [12]

3.4 From Improvisation to composition through Kinesthesis 2.0

Kinesthesis 2.0 reimagines the role of the performer, transforming them into an instant composer and improviser within the theatrical and musical landscape. This paradigm shift stems from the tool's ability to enable real-time structuring of soundscapes, where the interplay of gesture, voice, and technology creates a dynamic and ever-evolving sonic environment.

By enabling performers to navigate and manipulate sonic parameters dynamically, Kinesthesis 2.0 significantly expands the improvisational palette. Through the integration of a facial expression and hand gesture detection system, developed using MediaPipe in Python, and advanced audio processing tools in MAX/MSP—including a four-voice vocoder, pitch-shifter, reverb, multi-tap delay, and reverse delay—performers gain unparalleled control over their vocal output. Movements of the face, head, or hands are tracked in real-time to adjust the parameters of these effects, enabling the creation of expressive vocal effects and digital choir-like textures. [12]

This setup empowers performers to sculpt complex vocal timbres and rhythms in real-time, transcending the constraints of precomposed elements. They evolve into active composers, dynamically shaping vocalscapes "in vivo." This practice reflects the ethos of contemporary composers who pioneered the use of electronic apparatus to create seminal works, bridging the gap between human intuition and technological innovation. By merging gesture-based input with advanced audio processing, Kinesthesis 2.0 not only redefines improvisation but also expands the boundaries of what can be achieved in live performance.

4. CREATIVE PRACTICES, VOCAL INTERTEXTUALITY, AND INTERMEDIALITY IN KINESTHESIS

Kinesthesis draws from gestural controllers such as the eMic, which mapped physical inputs to vocal effects. [18] However, it extends these capabilities by integrating traditional gestures into modern technological frameworks, enabling performers to connect with both historical and contemporary audiences. This connection is deepened through the intertextuality of the voice, a concept rooted in theater and experimental performance, which refers to the layering of meaning and aesthetic expression in sound.

Intertextuality and intermediality play a transformative role in shaping modern performance by weaving together multiple texts, media, and sensory experiences to create deeply layered artistic expressions. Intertextuality in

performance involves referencing, reinterpreting, or juxtaposing existing texts—whether literary, visual, or cultural—within new contexts, fostering dialogue between past and present meanings. This dialogic interaction enables performers to question traditional narratives, highlight cultural intersections, and generate new interpretations that resonate with contemporary audiences. [20] Intermediality complements this by integrating diverse media forms, such as video, sound, digital technologies, and live performance, into a unified artistic experience. As López-Varela Azcárate (2011) emphasizes, intermediality highlights the dialogic process that occurs between different expressive media, revealing the materiality and medi-ality of cultural practices across time periods [21]

Together, intertextuality and intermediality transform the voice and body into instruments of abstraction and innovation, navigating between narrative clarity and experimental exploration.

In Kinesthesia 2.0, this intertextuality is amplified through the modulation of vocal timbres, dynamics, and textures in real time. By incorporating gestures and facial expressions as control mechanisms, Kinesthesia transforms the voice into a tangible, aesthetic experience, allowing it to embody complex, intangible forces. No longer confined to storytelling, the voice becomes an instrument of abstraction and innovation, navigating between narrative clarity and experimental exploration. This interplay aligns with established practices in theater and experimental performance, where the voice transcends linguistic meaning to operate as a medium for aesthetic transformation, forging a profound connection with audiences.

Artaud’s concept of glossolalia further illustrates the expressive potential of the voice. For Artaud, glossolalia bridges the semantic gap through vocal modulations, where rhythm, respiration, and the energy centers of the body convey meaning beyond traditional language. This retrospective exploration, akin to an excavation of the “Universal body,” transforms vocalization into an act that pretends to be language while resonating with audiences on a primal level. De Certeau builds upon this, asserting that glossolalia is not a language but a vocalization that transcends linguistic borders, initiating a reception of meaning that connects the performer and audience in a deeply visceral manner. [22]

5. ANTIGONE’S LAMENT: INTEGRATING KINESTHESIS 2.0 AND SOMAX2 FOR HUMAN-AI CO-CREATION

This performance draws inspiration from Antigone, a powerful symbol of resistance and freedom, whose lament provides a poignant cultural and emotional foundation for the exploration of human- AI interaction in musical performance. Somax2, a corpus-based machine learning system, is designed for real-time musical improvisation. By analyzing pre-recorded materials, it generates context-aware responses that mimic the nuances of live performance. [23] For this project, Somax2 was trained on a corpus of Epirotic dirge clarinet recordings, allowing it to reinterpret the melodic and rhythmic patterns characteristic of

Figure 8. Somax2.

this traditional lament, Somax2 was detecting onsets using a low-latency spectral flux algorithm (adapted from LibROSA [24]) to segment incoming audio into musical phrases. Extracting melodic/rhythmic motifs via Yin-based pitch tracking (monophonic input) or chroma features (polyphonic input) and generating responses by mapping these features to its corpus of Epirotic lament patterns, updated in real-time through continuous listening. This bidirectional flow enables improvisational dialogue, where the AI’s output evolves alongside the performer’s gestures and vocals see Fig. 8.

Kinesthesia 2.0 was employed to process the performer’s voice in real-time, transforming Antigone’s lament lyrics—“ὄρᾱτ’ ἔμ’, ὦ γὰρ πατρίας πολῖται... ἀλλ’ Ἀχέροντι νυμφεύσω”—into a lament aria. The system applied dynamic vocal effects, such as reverb and delay, to enhance the expressivity of the performance. Using gestures and facial expressions, the performer modulated vocal textures in real time, creating a deeply embodied musical experience. A custom graphic score, see Fig. 9, guides the performer in real-time interaction with Kinesthesia 2.0, detailing specific gestural movements to control parameters like pitch, reverb, delay, and glissando. This visual framework bridges the gap between physical gestures and sonic transformations, ensuring an intuitive and expressive

Figure 9. Graphic Score.

performance.

Each line of Antigone’s lament is accompanied by a corresponding mudra (symbolic hand gesture) that adds a layer of embodied meaning to the performance:

a. ὄρατ’ ἔμ’, ὦ γὰς πατρίας πολῖται (“Look at me, O citizens of my native land”): The Pathaka mudra symbolizes addressing or calling attention to a group, emphasizing Antigone’s plea to her people.

b. τὰν νεάταν ὁδὸν στεῖχουσας (“Treading the final path”): The Karthareemukham mudra represents a journey or road, reflecting Antigone’s walk toward her fate.

c. νέατον δὲ φέγγος λεύσσοις ἀελίου (“Looking upon the last light of the sun”): The Thripathaka mudra, symbolizing celestial objects like the sun, conveys the poignant imagery of her final gaze at life.

d. ἀλλὰ μὲν ὁ παγκοίτας Ἄιδας ζῶσαν ἄγει (“But Hades, who takes all, leads me away alive”): The Shikharam mudra signifies divine power or a higher force, embodying Hades as the inevitable pull of death.

e. τὰν Ἀχέρωντος ἀχτάν (“To the shore of Acheron”): The Sarpasirassu mudra represents flowing water or rivers, vividly portraying the journey to the underworld.

f. οὐθ’ ὑμενάων ἔγκληρον (“Not as a bride’s inheritance”): The Hamsasyam mudra, symbolizing delicate or fleeting concepts, reflects the grief of unfulfilled dreams.

g. οὐτ’ ἐπὶ νυμφεῖος πῶ μέ τις ὕμνος ὕμνησεν (“Nor was any hymn sung for my wedding”): The Kapitham mudra, substituted here to express sorrow, underscores the tragic absence of joy in Antigone’s life.

h. ἀλλ’ Ἀχέρωντι νυμφεύσω (“But I shall marry Acheron”): The Ardachandram mudra represents union or connection, tragically reinterpreted as her connection to death.

These mudras, integrated with the graphic score, guide the performer in blending traditional symbolic gestures with the technological processes of Kinesthesia 2.0. This

combination allows for a rich and multilayered interpretation of Antigone’s lament, elevating the performance from a simple interaction with technology to a deeply embodied exploration of human emotion and cultural symbolism.

As the aria unfolds, Somax2 interacts with Kinesthesia 2.0 by generating clarinet-based improvisations that complement the processed vocal improvisation. This bidirectional interaction enables a dynamic dialogue between the performer’s physical gestures and Somax2’s generative responses, resulting in a hybrid performance that combines traditional and computational approaches. By integrating Kinesthesia 2.0 and Somax2, this project demonstrates the potential of human-AI co-creation to reinterpret cultural heritage through interactive media. The combination of embodied performance techniques and real-time machine learning offers a novel framework for exploring the human-computer collaboration in musical improvisation. A recording of *Antigone’s Lament*, showcasing the live interaction between Kinesthesia 2.0 and Somax2, is available on SoundCloud: Antigone’s Lament audio file³.

6. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

6.1 Technical Challenges

Achieving seamless synchronization between gestures and audio outputs remains a critical challenge. The system’s complexity also demands extensive training, requiring performers to develop technical fluency alongside artistic expression

6.2 Opportunities for Innovation

- **AI-Driven Adaptation:** Incorporating machine learning could refine gesture recognition and personalization.
- **Expanded Applications:** Kinesthesia tools could be applied to dance, multimedia installations, and experimental music.
- **Audience Interaction:** Developing systems that respond to audience movements or sounds could enhance immersion, creating a reciprocal relationship between performers and spectators.

7. CONCLUSIONS

Kinesthesia tools exemplify the transformative potential of interactive media in theatrical performance, bridging the rich traditions of cultural expression with the innovations of contemporary technology. By integrating gesture and facial expression tracking with advanced audio processing, Kinesthesia 2.0 enables performers to become instant composers, dynamically shaping soundscapes through their physical and vocal expressions. This approach not only preserves the symbolic depth of historical practices, such as the Greek schemata and Kathakali mudras, but also reimagines their applications in a digital context.

³ <https://soundcloud.com/tilemachos-moussas/antigones-lament>

The collaborative potential of these tools is further highlighted through their integration with AI systems like Somax2. By processing Antigone's lament lyrics into a dynamic lament aria and pairing it with Somax2's generative reinterpretations of Epirotic *μοιρολόι*, the performance demonstrates a novel dialogue between human emotion and machine intelligence. This co-creative interplay underscores the evolving role of the performer, who navigates between tradition and innovation to create a hybrid, multi-sensory experience.

The implications of this work extend beyond the stage, offering a framework for the broader integration of interactive media in the arts. By situating the body as a central instrument of communication and creativity, Kinesthesia tools encourage a deeper engagement with the possibilities of embodiment, technology, and co-creation. As the boundaries of human-AI collaboration continue to expand, Kinesthesia stands as a testament to the enduring power of performance to connect audiences with timeless themes in profoundly new ways.

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